

 Federal Office
of Metrology and
Surveying

GGOS Outreach Activities

Merging Efforts with IAG

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BEV - Federal Office of Metrology and Surveying (Austria)

GGOS Days 2023

Thursday, September 21, 2023

Alcalá de Henares, Spain

Website of GGOS

Federal Office
of Metrology and
Surveying

www.ggos.org

Information Portal

SERVICES

OBSERVATIONS

PRODUCTS

Easy understandable descriptions

Height Reference Frame

What is a height above sea level?

A height system is a **one-dimensional coordinate system** used to express the metric distance (height) of a **point above a reference surface** (i.e., the zero-height level). Traditionally, the reference surface is linked to the **mean sea level** and the heights are determined using **geodetic levelling techniques**. These techniques measure the distance between two **equipotential or level surfaces** of the **Earth's gravity field** and provide the height along the curved plumb line. The mean sea level serving as the zero-height level is inferred from averaged **tide gauge records** over certain time intervals and the heights are determined along the so-called vertical or levelling networks. As the tide gauges register the local sea level and the vertical networks cover limited regions, these systems are known as local height systems. Presently, there are about **hundred local and regional height systems** in use, and they exhibit discrepancies with respect to each other up to ± 2 m.

Local zero-height levels (A and B) depending on the mean sea level registered at individual tide gauges and the global zero-height reference level defined by the International Height Reference System (IHRF) and its realisation, the International Height Reference Frame (IHRF)

The **International Height Reference System (IHRF)** is a **global unified height system**: the zero-height level is a global equipotential surface of the Earth's gravity field and the vertical coordinate of any point on the Earth's surface is the level difference with respect to that global equipotential surface. Heights referring to the IHRF are consistent globally and **do not depend on the local sea levels**. The realisation of the IHRF is the International Height Reference Frame (IHRF): a set of reference stations homogeneously distributed

Data Sources

IERS

International Earth Rotation and Reference Systems Service (IERS)

IERS EARTH ORIENTATION CENTRE

The IERS Earth Orientation Centre is responsible for monitoring of long-term EOP, publications of time dissemination and leap second announcements. It is located at the Observatoire de Paris in France

IERS RAPID SERVICE/PREDICTION CENTRE

The IERS Rapid Service/Prediction Centre is responsible for providing predicted EOP and measured EOP at a rapid turnaround basis, primarily for real-time users and others needing EOP information more rapidly. It is located at the United States Naval Observatory (USNO) in Washington D.C., USA.

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Further Information

IERS Conventions (2010). Gérard Petit and Brian Luzum (eds.), (IERS Technical Note ; 36) Frankfurt am Main: Verlag des Bundesamts für Kartographie und Geodäsie, 2010. 179 pp., ISBN 3-89888-989-6

Information Portal

Federal Office
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23 geodetic products

www.ggos.org/products

GGOS Website
www.ggos.org

Information Portal

Federal Office
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13 geodetic observation techniques

www.ggos.org/obs

GGOS Website
www.ggos.org

GGOS Website - Usage Statistic

Federal Office
of Metrology and
Surveying

Total visits: ≈ **140 k** (2.5 years)

Visits/day: ≈ **200** (now)

Federal Office
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Video Production

„Discover GGOS and Geodesy“ film

- Describing:
 - Geodesy and GGOS
 - Observations, Products, Services
- Long (8 min) and short (1.5 min) version
- Very successful: > **14,000 views** (1.5 years)
- Growing subscribers for GGOS YouTube Channel

Scan to watch it

youtube.com/@iag-ggos

„Discover GGOS“ film - Languages

- Extend range of this film
- Translated and recorded by volunteers of the geodetic community (12 versions)

Scan to watch

Federal Office
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IUGG

Global Geodetic
Observing System

Language	Publish Date
EN English	February 2022
ZH Chinese	July 2023 NEW
ES Spanish	February 2022
FR French	April 2022
AR Arabic	August 2022
PT Portuguese	May 2022
DE German	February 2022
FA Farsi	December 2022
JP Japanese	February 2022
IT Italian	July 2022
NL Dutch	July 2022
BG Bulgarian	July 2022

„Terrestrial Reference Frame“ film

- Published on **September 13**
- 10 minutes video
- Describing:
 - Why TRF is important?
 - How TRF contributes to Science and Society?
- Available in **8 languages** (more will follow)
- Many views so far: **> 5000**

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Trailer

please share
this video

Scan to watch it

Future: Further Videos Production

- Videos about further geodetic products
 - Film about „Geoid“
 - ...
- Everyone is invited to contribute
 - **Translation** into other language
 - **Ideas** for new education films
 - Providing attractive **footage or graphics**
 - Get in contact with us: co@ggos.org

Federal Office
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Surveying

Subscribe for the
GGOS YouTube Channel
youtube.com/@iag-ggos

GGOS – Social Media Channels

Federal Office
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X (Twitter)
started in 2016
twitter.com/IAG_GGOS

LinkedIn
started in May 2021
linkedin.com/company/iag-ggos

YouTube
started in June 2021
youtube.com/@iag-ggos

GGOS Newsletter
started in 2020
ggos.org/newsletter

Facebook
started in Dec. 2021
[GGOS @ Facebook](https://GGOS@Facebook)

**Please subscribe to our
Social Media Channels**

Create Further Value in Future

See further presentations in next session today
„Making Geodetic Data & Products FAIR“

Merging Outreach Efforts within IAG

Communication & Outreach

- **IAG, GGOS** and other **IAG** components
- **Common outreach activities in future:**
 - Create a common strategy
 - Merging efforts
 - Prevent duplication of tasks

Federal Office
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One common internet presence

- Refresh IAG website (GGOS website design)
- Merge GGOS website with IAG website
- New & better recognizable domain

www.ggos.org

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www.iag-aig.org

Future: one domain for all

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Entrance door
to Geodesy and IAG:

geodesy.science

iag.geodesy.science

ggos.geodesy.science

Other IAG Sub-Components, e.g.:

com2.geodesy.science

iccm.geodesy.science

Future Information Portal:

products.geodesy.science

obs.geodesy.science

services.geodesy.science

Proposal: Reduce duplications

- Common **Blog and Newsletter** structure of IAG & GGOS

- Centralized **Event Calender** over all IAG components

- Joint **Social Media Channels** and **Video Platform** of IAG & GGOS

- Joint **Outreach Materials**

Can be realized in the next years

Promotion at Conferences

Federal Office of Metrology and Surveying

IAG-GGOS booth at IUGG General Assembly 2023 in Berlin (July 2023)

Advancing Geodesy Together

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